

A NEW COMPLEX COMPOUND OF RHENIUM

BY R. D. DAFTARY AND B. C. HALDAR

A new complex compound of rhenium has been prepared by the interaction of diphenylcarbazide and potassium perrhenate. When acetone solution of diphenylcarbazide is added slowly to ice-cold potassium perrhenate solution in 8*N*-HCl, deep violet solids are formed. These are separated after an hour by centrifugation, dissolved in minimum quantity of acetone, and reprecipitated by dropwise addition of 10*N*-HCl. The solids are removed, washed twice with ice-cold water, and then taken up in chloroform. Any residue remaining is rejected.

The violet coloured compound is obtained by evaporation of the chloroform solution. On drying at 110° it loses weight and changes into a substance, insoluble in chloroform. So it is dried in a vacuum desiccator. It is insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents, such as, acetone, acetophenone, etc.

Transport experiment with acetone solution of the complex, containing free hydrochloric acid, indicates that it is a non-electrolyte. The results of chemical analysis of the compound suggest its formula as $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}_2\text{DPO}]_x$, where DPO represents a molecule of diphenylcarbazone less one hydrogen atom, and x is an integer. {Found: C, 28.86; H, 2.24; O (by diff), 10.62; N, 9.98; Cl, 13.2; Re, 35.1. $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}_2\text{DPO}]_x$ requires C, 29.43; H, 2.47; O, 9.05; N, 10.56; Cl, 13.37; Re, 35.12%}. The value of x in the empirical formula of the complex has been determined from the depression of the freezing point of acetophenone and is found to be 0.88, suggesting the simple formula $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}_2\text{DPO}]$ for the complex. Magnetic susceptibility measurements show that the complex is diamagnetic.

The absorption spectra of the complex in acetone and chloroform solutions show maxima at around 540 $m\mu$ in the visible region; the molar extinction coefficients of the complex in acetone and chloroform solutions, measured at 540 $m\mu$, are 6853 and 6619 $\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ respectively. Absorption measurements have been taken with Unicam S.P. 500 spectrophotometer using 1 cm cells. Although the compound is insoluble in water, the violet colour of the acetone solution disappears by the addition of water. Further work is in progress.

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. P. B. Sarkar, Head of the Chemistry Department, Calcutta University, for giving laboratory facilities for magnetic measurements and to Principal, Y. G. Naik for allowing them to use the spectrophotometer of the Physics Department, Gujarat College, Ahmedabad. Grateful acknowledgements are due to the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, Government of India, for the award of a senior research scholarship to one of them (R. D. Daftary).

* Present address: Health Physics Division, Atomic Energy Establishment, Trombay.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
GUJARAT COLLEGE, AHMEDABAD,
AND
INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BOMBAY.

Received June 4, 1960.